

Synthesis and Reactions of Triphenyl(4-t-butylphenoxy)tin(IV)

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Compared to a considerable and growing interest in the chemistry of organotin compounds because of their manifold applications¹, scattered references are available on the synthesis of organotin phenoxy derivatives². Some of these derivatives have been reported to be very useful in synthetic chemistry³. In view of this, we have undertaken the synthesis of triphenyl(4-t-butylphenoxy)tin(IV) and its reactivity has been studied.

Results and Discussion

The formation of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t-4)$ (**1**) by the reaction of Ph_3SnCl with sodium salt of 4-t-butylphenol in THF/methanol mixture with immediate separation of quantitative NaCl can be represented as

Stoichiometric composition of the compound has been confirmed by elemental analyses. It is a high melting white solid but soluble in most of the common organic solvents. Molar conductance value of $10^{-3}M$ solution of the compound in nitrobenzene, suggests it to be a non-electrolyte while molecular weight determination in the same solvent indicates it to be a monomer.

Ir spectrum of the compound shows a significant lowering of ν_{C-O} mode of the free ligand, 4-Bu^tC₆H₄ONa from 1225 to 1150 cm⁻¹ in the complex suggesting coordination through oxygen to the metal. This has been further confirmed by the appearance of a new band around 550 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-O}$ mode⁴. Polymerisation of the compound through aryloxy groups has been excluded because of the absence of any band due to $\text{Sn}-O \rightarrow \text{Sn}$, expected to occur at lower regions than the terminal $\nu_{\text{Sn}-O}$ mode. A band around 230 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder at 225 cm⁻¹ has been

assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn}-\text{Ph}}$ modes. Based upon these observations, a tetrahedral environment around tin may be proposed for compound **1**.

In order to explore the reactivity of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t-4)$, its reactions have been carried out under the following categories.

Reactions of 1 with carboxylic acids : Compound **1** reacts with different carboxylic acids in benzene under reflux when solid organotin carboxylates separate out from the solution,

where R is CH₃, CH₂Cl, CCl₃, C₆H₅, *o*-CH₃OC₆H₄ and *o*-OHC₆H₄. Fine crystals of *p*-t-butylphenol was isolated from the filtrate which thereby confirms the above mode of reaction. The exact stoichiometric composition of these carboxylates was established not only by elemental analysis but also by their melting points which corresponded with the carboxylates reported in literature prepared by different synthetic routes⁵.

In the ir spectra of the isolated carboxylates, the difference between asym(OCO) and sym(OCO) has been taken as a good criterion to decide about the denticity of the carboxylate ligands⁶. A difference of the order of ~ 150 cm⁻¹ indicates the carboxylate moiety to act as bridging or bidentate ligand⁷ whereas a difference greater than 200 cm⁻¹ shows their monodentate behaviour⁸. Thus differences of 120, 170, 110 and 105 cm⁻¹ observed in the asym(OCO) and sym(OCO) modes (Δ_{OCO}) in the ir spectra of $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOCH}_3$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOCH}_2\text{Cl}$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-}o$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OH-}o$ respectively, suggest the carboxylate moiety to act as a bridging or bidentate ligand. However for $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOCCl}_3$, the Δ_{OCO} value (350 cm⁻¹) clearly indicates the monodentate nature of the

trichloroacetate group.

Reaction of CH_3COCl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}$ and HCl : When hydrogen chloride gas was allowed to pass through a chloroform solution of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t)$ for about 3 h followed by refluxing, a white solid was obtained. It was identified as Ph_3SnCl indicated by its elemental analysis and melting point. The 1 : 1 reaction of the compound with CH_3COCl and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}$ resulted into the formation of Ph_3SnCl and $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t$ respectively. These observations may be rationalised as

Reactions with alkali metal phenoxides : Conductometric titrations of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t)$ with alkali metal (4-t-butylphenoxides) in nitrobenzene at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ have revealed sharp breaks in the conductance composition curves at 1 : 2 molar ratio. This suggests the formation of a double salts as

where M is Li, Na and K.

Based on this, compounds of the above composition have been isolated by 1 : 2 reaction of the parent compound with different alkali metal phenoxides in chloroform. Elemental analyses of the compounds agree well with their proposed formula.

Experimental

Ph_3SnCl was recrystallised from THF. Sodium salt of $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t$ 4 was prepared by reacting it with sodium metal in benzene. Solvents used were dried by standard methods. Carboxylic acids were purified by the literature method. Tin was estimated as SnO_2 . IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrophotometers.

$\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t)$ (1) : To a solution of

Ph_3SnCl (4.5 g, 0.011 mol) in THF was added an equimolar solution of $\text{NaOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t$ 4 (2.00 g, 0.011 mol) in methanol. The well stirred mixture was refluxed when a white solid (NaCl) separated out. It was filtered and from the filtrate the product was obtained by the addition of petroleum ether (b.p. $40\text{--}60^\circ$). The solid was recrystallised from benzene and dried under reduced pressure (80%) (Found : C, 67.41; H, 5.58; Sn, 23.90. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{28}\text{OSn}$ requires : C, 67.33; H, 5.61; Sn, 23.48); ν_{max} 1150(C-O), 550(Sn-O) and 230cm^{-1} (Sn-Ph).

Reactions of 1 with carboxylic acids : To a benzene solution of 1 were added different carboxylic acids in 1 : 1 pre-determined molar ratios. The reactants were refluxed and the resulting solids were washed with petroleum ether (b.p. $40\text{--}60^\circ$) and dried under reduced pressure : $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOCH}_3$, (m.p. 124°) (Found : C, 58.55; H, 4.25; Sn, 29.06. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{Sn}$ requires : C, 58.67; H, 4.40; Sn, 29.09%); $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOCH}_2\text{Cl}$, (183°) (Found : C, 54.18; H, 3.60; Sn, 26.79. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{ClSn}$ requires : C, 54.11; H, 3.83; Sn, 26.83%); $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOC}_6\text{H}_5$, (85°) (Found : C, 63.59; H, 4.31; Sn, 25.21. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{Sn}$ requires : C, 63.69; H, 4.24; Sn, 25.26%); $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe}$, (108°) (Found : C, 62.25; H, 4.45; Sn, 23.79. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3\text{Sn}$ requires : C, 62.31; H, 4.39; Sn, 23.75%); $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnOCOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OH-}o$, 124° (Found : C, 61.88; H, 4.09; Sn, 24.51. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{Sn}$ requires : C, 61.64; H, 4.11; Sn, 24.43%).

Reactions of 1 with alkali metal phenoxides : By following the above procedure, compounds of composition $\text{M}_2[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Bu}^t)_3]$ were obtained : $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{OSnLi}_2$ (Found : C, 73.89; H, 7.01; Sn, 15.31. Requires : C, 73.94; H, 6.93; Sn, 15.27%); $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{OSnNa}_2$ (Found : C, 70.82; H, 6.71; Sn, 14.62. Requires : C, 71.02; H, 6.65; Sn, 14.67%); $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{OSnK}_2$ (Found : C, 68.24; H, 6.48; Sn, 14.72. Requires : C, 68.32; H, 6.40; Sn, 14.67%).

The same procedure was followed for carrying out the reactions of 1 with CH_3COCl and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}$, while HCl gas was passed through the solution of 1 in chloroform.

NOTE

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